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Electrical behavior (ac And dc Conduction) of Polythiophene composite thin films doped with Iodine.

Abstract: - Thin solid films of PTh-PVAc doped with Iodine (Pure, 5.5, 10.4, 14.9, 18.9 and 22.5 wt %) were synthesized by chemical oxidative polymerization method in order to study the electrical properties such as dc and ac conductivity at various temperature ranges. Amorphous nature of the sample was confirmed by the XRD technique of sample. Temperature dependent conductivity (313-363K) of PTh-PVAc films doped with Iodine follows Arrhenius nature which depicts dc parameters such as activation energy, pre-exponential factors etc. The impedance spectra of films (323-343K over frequencies from 0.1-200 KHz) found to consist of only one arc suggest various parameters such as relaxation time, bulk resistance, bulk capacitance, dielectric activation energy etc.

Keywords: Poly(vinyl acetate) (PVAc), Polythiophene (PTh), Iodine, dc,ac

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to electron hopping transport, PTh is arose as a better conducting polymer and a leading field of investigation amongst conducting polymers. A number of applications have been proposed for PThs, such as field effect transistors, electroluminescent devices, solar cells, photochemical resists, nonlinear optic devices, batteries, diodes and chemical sensors [1]. A high performance is seen in various electronic devices and memory devices of PTh conductive polymers, due to recent developments of materials having improved process ability and ambient stability relative to the earlier systems. Due to high conductivity and fascinating structural properties, PTh has been involved in a wide range of applications.

These conjugating polymers thin films have been studied by many workers, because of special electrical properties, considerable thermal stability and oxidation resistance that are favorable in applications such as optoelectronic, biosensors, electro chromic displays and chemical sensors [2-3]. Roncali [4] surveyed the electrochemical synthesis and the electronic properties of substituted PThs in 1997. The overall review on chemical synthesis of PThs and applications as chemical sensors, organic memory devices, photo conductivity, etc., is given by many researchers [5,6]. Temperature-dependent conductivity, in the case of ion conducting solid electrolytes, is more completely explained by Vogel-Tamman-Fulcher (VTF) [7-9] rather than other models. Ryu et al. [10] predicted that PTh powder prepared by electrochemical method, shows better results than that prepared by the fast oxidation method. Yildiz et al. [11] synthesized poly (ethylene oxide)-copolymer-polythiophene (PEO-co-PTh) by electrochemical copolymerization and from characterization, they predicted the exploitation of electrochromic devices. Barde et al [12] observed the variation in ionic conductivity in polypyrrole (PPy)-poly (vinyl acetate) (PVAc) films synthesized by oxidative polymerization. An investigation in electrical, structural properties and impedance spectroscopy in PTh-PVAc composite films doped with Iodine was carried out by Bobade et al and Deshmukh et al [13-14].

The present paper focuses on comparison in electrical properties of Polythiophene composite thin films doped with Iodine.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A) STRUCTURE

For structure determination, X-ray diffractometer PANalytical PW: 3040/60, Netherland was used. All the PTh PVAc samples doped with iodine were characterized at Vishveshwariya National Institute of Technology (VNIT), Nagpur.

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B) DC CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENT

The dc conductivity of the samples was measured by the two probe method [12, 13], in a temperature range of 313 – 363 K. A dc regulated power supply and a picoammeter with a resolution of 1 pA was used for the measurement of resistance of the sample. Samples being tested were sandwiched between two conducting copper electrodes of the sample holder and then placed in a muffle furnace. The heating rate of the sample was $1^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$.

C) AC CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENT

ac conductivity of the samples was recorded on LCR meter (Wayne Kerr, UK) having range of frequencies from 0.1-200 KHz at temperature in the range 323-343K with heating rate $1^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. A constant voltage is applied to the sample and corresponding impedance and phase angle was measured at constant temperature for all frequency range. Sample holder and furnace used is same as that of dc conductivity measurement.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A) STRUCTURE

The XRD spectra of the PTh-PVAc composite films with different wt % of Iodine are shown in the figure 1.

Fig 1 XRD Spectra of PTh-PVAc films doped with Iodine

Absence of peak in the intensity versus 2θ curve represents complete amorphous state of the sample [6]. Indication of peak or peaks in the curve suggests the formation of phase or phases in the composite during polymerization process.

All the spectra for different PThs having wt % of Iodine reveal a hump in low 2θ region. It is due to short range order and indicating that these PTh-PVAc composite films doped with Iodine are amorphous. Increase in concentration of dopant Iodine does not induce any crystallinity in these composite films. This also explains the homogeneous nature of the samples. The sharp peaks observed may be due to presence of Iodine in the sample. Since the samples of PTh-PVAc films doped with Iodine were indicating total amorphous nature this characterization is limited for these films only.

B) DC CONDUCTIVITY OF PTH-PVAC FILMS DOPED WITH IODINE

The dc conductivity of samples of iodine wt % 5.5 – 22.5 was measured at a temperature range of 313 – 363 K, by measuring the resistance of the samples; it was observed that the conductivity depends upon composition as well as temperature. The variation of DC conductivity vs. concentration of iodine wt % for composite films at

330 K is shown in Figure1. Initially, the conductivity increased, reached $9.78 \times 10^{-10} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for 10.4 wt % of iodine and then rapidly decreased with iodine concentration.

Fig.2: Variation of Conductivity with Iodine wt % at 330 K

Many researchers [11, 14-16] reported a similar conductivity isotherm. In the case of PTh composites [16-20], percolation behavior was reported even for a low concentration of PTh. The temperature dependence of conductivity for different iodine wt % is shown in Figure 2. From this plot it is observed that the conductivity increased with increase in temperature, due to an increase in mobility of the ions. Ionic conductivity for 10.4 wt % of iodine showed maximum conductivity, which can be attributed to the fact that ionic motion is improved by polymer segmental motion for the particular concentration. Also the formation of PTh-PVAc^{-I} has much contribution to the ionic conductivity.

Fig. 3: Variation of logσ with 1/T for different wt. % of Iodine

From the fig.3 it is observed that initially the rate of increase of conductivity is fast and after certain temperature the rise is slow. Thus it leads to two activation region (I and II as shown in fig.3) giving two different activation energies. The samples synthesized by concentration of Iodine (5.5, 10.4, 14.9 and 22.5 wt %), show the curvature type behavior below a certain temperature T_c , called knee temperature, and above which the curves are nearly linear in nature. The non-linearity in Arrhenius plot for samples synthesized at 5.5, 10.4, 14.9 and 22.5 wt % of Iodine indicates the ionic transport facilitates by the segmental motion of polymer chains. Thus Vogel-Tamman-Fulcher (VTF) [9-11] equation may more effectively represent the results. And the sample with 18.9 wt % of Iodine indicates straight line nature to which VTF equation could not be applied.

$$\sigma = \frac{A}{T^{1/2}} \exp\left[-\frac{B}{k(T - T_0)}\right] \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature; 'A', 'B' and T₀ are the fitting constants and 'k' is Boltzmann constant. 'A' is the pre-exponential factor, which is related to the number of charge carriers. 'B' is the pseudo activation energy related to activation energy of the ion transport. It is related to critical volume for displacement in free volume model [9] and to the energy barrier for rotational motion of polymer segment in configuration entropy model [21]. T₀ is the critical (ideal glass transition) temperature, usually it is 30-50 K below 'T_g'. It is the temperature at which configuration entropy or free volume disappears.

Fig. 4 VTF plots for PTh-PVAc films for different wt % of

The exploration of equation 1) gives the VTF fit parameters (fig.4) which are summarized in Table 1. It is evident that the activation energy value 'B', for the sample prepared with 5.5 wt % of Iodine is minimum. The values of T₀ increases with rise in concentration of Iodine. Such dependence of T₀, with respect to concentration of salt, has been reported in polymer electrolytes [22]. In high temperature region (fig.3) the curves no longer fits the VTF equation. The cross over from VTF to Arrhenius is clearly visible in the high temperature region. This type of cross over in conductivity behavior generally observed in polymer electrolyte systems [9-11].

Arrhenius equation is,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp\left[-\frac{E_a}{kT}\right] \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where E_a is the Activation energy and σ₀ is the pre-exponential factor.

Table 1: VTF equation fitting parameters for the PTh-PVAc films for different Iodine wt %

Concentration of Iodine (wt%)	Ionic Transference number (tion)	Energy E _a (eV)	Temperature T _c (K)	Pre-exponential factor A (SK ^{1/2} cm ⁻¹)	Pseudo activation energy B(eV)	Ideal glass transition temperature T _o (K)
5.5	0.96	0.149	388	2.3319 x10 ⁻⁷	0.00009	327
10.4	0.94	0.188	385	1.6538 x10 ⁻⁷	0.00019	330
14.9	0.95	0.420	362	1.0124 x10 ⁻⁸	0.00058	332
22.5	0.87	0.150	380	1.7047 x10 ⁻⁸	0.00010	341

B) AC CONDUCTIVITY OF PTh-PVAc FILMS DOPED WITH IODINE

ac conductivity of the pure PTh-PVAc sample and doped with different Iodine wt % was measured at various temperatures 323-343K by applying a wide range of frequencies from 0.1-200 KHz. Fig.5-8 shows Nyquist plots of the samples Pure, 5.5 wt%,10.4 wt% and 14.9 wt% samples and it is observed that the resistance of all the samples is found to be decreasing with the rise in temperature.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

All the curves show the same trends in the temperature range 323-343 K. Many researchers [23-26] reported a similar conductivity isotherm. The impedance spectrum of PTh-PVAc pure film and doped with Iodine is found to consist of only one arc (fig. 5-8) which may be taken to mean that the conduction processes have identical time constants [27].

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

All the curves show the same trends in the temperature range 323-343 K. Many researchers [23-26] reported a similar conductivity isotherm. The impedance spectrum of PTh-PVAc pure film and doped with Iodine is found to consist of only one arc (fig. 5-8) which may be taken to mean that the conduction processes have identical time constants [27].

Also it may be argued that as the temperature increases the arc of semicircle reduces, indicating the increase in conductivity. The basic features of the spectra seem to be qualitatively similar to those obtained by Johnson et al. [28] for polythiophene films and Komura et al. [24] for polypyrrole polystyrenesulfonate composite films in a similar configuration. The arcs are found to be highly depressed for the all films for different temperatures which indicate the distribution of relaxation times [29]. From the semicircle, the values of bulk resistance are calculated and noted in table 3.2.1. The variation of real axis Z' with $\log f$ for the samples is shown in fig 9-12.

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

From the fig.9-12, it is observed that the pure PTh-PVAc sample shows the wide variation of resistance with respect to real axis at all frequencies. As the frequency increases the resistance of the sample is found to be decreasing in a continuous manner and then it became constant. Also as the concentration of the dopant Iodine is increasing, the sample exhibits much lesser resistance for higher frequencies. The values of resistance are decreasing with rise in frequency and temperature. The magnitude decreases on increasing temperature in the low- frequency range which merges in the high-frequency region irrespective of temperature. This nature may be due to the release of space charge [30].

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

The reduction in barrier properties of the materials with rise in temperature may be a responsible factor for enhancement of ac conductivity of the materials at higher frequencies [31-32]. Further, in the low frequency region, there is a decrease in magnitude with rise in temperature showing negative temperature coefficient of resistance (NTCR) behavior [33]. This behavior is changed drastically in the high frequency region showing complete merge of plot above a certain fixed frequency.

Fig. 13

Fig. 14

The variation of log f versus Z'' in fig. 13-16 shows asymmetric peaks at different temperatures. Each peak is associated with a maximum frequency called as relaxation frequency (f_r). As the temperature increases the relaxation frequency is found to be shifting towards higher frequency side and it finally merges in the high frequency region which is an indication of the accumulation of space charge in materials.

Fig. 15

Fig. 16

The relaxation frequency (f_r) follows the Arrhenius behavior as,

$$f_r = f_0 \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{kT}\right)$$

Or

(3.2.1)

$$\tau = \tau_0 \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{kT}\right)$$

This equation is explored to find out the dielectric relaxation activation energy (ΔE) and relaxation time (τ). The calculated values of relaxation frequencies are plotted against the $1/T$ as shown in fig 17-19.

Fig. 17

Fig. 18

The variation of log fr versus $1/T$ for the sample pure, 5.5 wt% and 10.4 wt% shows a straight line nature [34-36]. From this straight lines dielectric relaxation activation energy (ΔE) and relaxation time (τ) is noted in table 2.

Fig. 19

Table 2 Dielectric relaxation activation energy and Relaxation time of PTh-PVAc film doped with Iodine

Sr.No.	Iodine wt %	ΔE (eV)	τ (μ s)
1	Pure PTh-PVAc	0.542	79.43
2	5.5	0.475	15.85
3	10.4	0.443	3.72
4	14.9	-	-

From the table 2 it is observed that, dielectric relaxation activation energy and relaxation time is maximum for Pure PTh-PVAc sample and minimum for 10.4 wt % of Iodine.

The values of bulk resistance (R_b) from fig. 5-8 and bulk capacitance (C_b) for peak frequencies from fig.9-12 are noted in table 3. From the table 3 it is observed that the bulk resistance of the sample decreases with the increase in temperature. The bulk capacitance is found to be maximum for the sample with 5.5 wt % Iodine.

Table 3 Bulk resistance and Bulk capacitance of PTh-PVAc film doped with Iodine at different temperature

Iodine wt %	323 K		328 K		333 K		338 K		343 K	
	$R_b(K\Omega)$	$C_b(pF)$								
Pure PTh-PVAc	4850	54.72	1550	51.36	690	57.69	400	66.68	275	64.26
5.5	120	331.74	51	312.22	25.1	317.20	15.1	351.51	10.2	390.28
10.4	11.8	202.31	5.6	213.27	3.1	256.83	2.2	-	1.4	-
14.9	1.6	-	0.99	-	0.61	-	0.42	-	0.33	-

IV. CONCLUSION

Amorphous nature of the sample was confirmed by the XRD technique of sample. Temperature dependant conductivity for the samples 5.5, 10.4, 14.9 and 22.5 wt % of Iodine dopant follows the VTF equation [7-9] except 18.9 wt % sample. The cross over from VTF to Arrhenius observed in present system may be due to some sort of transition in energetic of local ion motion and reduction in effective ion density on undergoing order-disorder transition at temperature T_c . Thus T_c can be linked to order-disorder temperature. Below T_c the curves follows VTF equation. When the ionic conduction follows the VTF equation, a linear relation between $\log(\sigma T^{1/2})$ and $1/(T - T_0)$ is expected as shown in fig.3.1.3. The impedance spectra of PTh-PVAc films doped with Iodine consist of only one arc which may be taken to mean that the conduction processes have identical time constants. The variation of real axis Z' with $\log f$ shows negative temperature coefficient of resistance (NTCR). The variation of imaginary axis Z'' versus $\log f$ shows asymmetric peaks at different temperatures that lead to Debye type of relaxation. On the basis of impedance spectra various parameters such as relaxation time, bulk resistance, bulk capacitance, dielectric activation energy etc. are calculated. Dielectric relaxation activation energy and relaxation time is maximum for Pure PTh-PVAc sample and minimum for 10.4 wt % of Iodine. The bulk capacitance is found to be maximum for the sample with 5.5 wt % Iodine.

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